

GROWTH AND CORM YIELD RESPONSE OF UPLAND COCOYAM (*Xanthosoma sagittifolium* L)
TO SAWDUST MULCH AND N P K 20 : 10 : 10 FERTILIZER RATES IN THE HUMID FOREST
ZONE OF NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

Cocoyam (*Xanthosoma sagittifolium* L) is the third ranking carbohydrate in Nigeria and is intensively cultivated and consumed by resource-poor farm families in Southeastern and Southwestern parts of the Country. The crop has high potential as a food security crop but yields are very low and adequate research attention is yet to be accorded the crop for increased productivity. This trial was aimed at developing a sustainable technology for increased productivity of the crop. A field trial was conducted in 2000/2001 and 2001/2002 cropping seasons at the Crop Research Farm of the University of Calabar in the humid rain forest zone of Southeastern Nigeria. The eight treatments studied were control (zero inputs), 20t/ha sawdust mulch, 200, 300 and 400 kg/ha of N P K 20:10:10 fertilizer rates applied sole and in combination with 20 t/ha sawdust mulch. A randomized complete block design (R C B) was used in three replications. The experiment showed that application of sawdust mulch and fertilizer consistently increased cocoyam yield with increasing rates of fertilizer applied. Sawdust mulch applied sole raise cocoyam yields above the control by 36% in 2000/2001 and 52% in 2001/2002. Combining sawdust mulch with any fertilizer rate resulted in significantly ($p = 0.05$) higher yield than when the fertilizer rate was applied sole. A combination of sawdust mulch and fertilizer applied at 200, 300 and 400 kg/ha produced higher yields by 3.4 t/ha (34%), 3.7 t/ha (29%), and 3.7 t/ha (19%) than the corresponding sole fertilizer rate in 2000/2001. Yield increases in 2001/2002 cropping were 5.7 t/ha (50%), 3.6 t/ha (26%) and 2.4 t/ha (13%) in the corresponding treatments. The highest cocoyam yields of 4.57 t/ha and 4.71 t/ha in 2000/2001 and 2001/2002 respectively were obtained by combining sawdust mulch with 400 kg/ha of N P K fertilizer. It could therefore be concluded that joint application of sawdust mulch and fertilizer is beneficial to cocoyam and farmers should combine 20 t/ha sawdust mulch with 400 kg/ha N P K fertilizer for high and sustainable productivity of cocoyam in the rain forest zone of Southeastern Nigeria.

KEY WORDS: Cocoyam yield, efficiency, fertilizer rates, humid forest, sawdust mulch.

INTRODUCTION

Cocoyam is an important staple tuber crop in the food economy of peasant farmers in the rain forest zone of southern Nigeria where it is cultivated in association with other food crops such as yam, maize, plantain, cassava and vegetables (Onwueme, 1978). The crop ranks third after cassava and yam in Nigeria (FOS, 1979) which accounts for the world's largest output of the crop with annual output of about 11 million metric tones (Horton *et al*; 1984; N R C R I, 1998). Previously, cocoyam had been regarded as "poor man's food" or woman's crop and as such has lagged behind the preferred stople root/tuber crops such as yam and cassava in research attention (Ezeh, 1987; Ezeh and Mbanoso, 1987; Ikwelle *et al*; 2003).

However, the crop has assumed nutritional and industrial significance in flour industries (Olatunji and Akinrele, 1978). In Nigeria its production is on the increase due to massive awareness created by the National Root Crop Research Institute (N R C R I, 1998) and the Cocoyam Growers Association of Nigeria (C G A N). Like other

Table 1. Effect of treatment on vegetative growths parameters of cocoyam *Xanthosoma sagittifolium* (L) in 2000/2001 and 2001/2002 cropping seasons at 4 months after planting (4 MAP).

Treatment	Cropping season							
	2000/2001				2001/2002			
	Plant height (cm)	No. Leaves/plant	LA (m ²)	LAI	Plant height (cm)	No. Leaves/plant	LA (m ²)	LAI
Control	44.0c	6.4b	132.74f	4.42d	38.3f	6.6d	127.38h	4.25f
Sawdust mulch	65.0c	7.3a	264.33e	8.81c	56.7e	7.1c	254.54g	8.48e
200kg NPK/ha	66.7c	6.8b	306.27c	10.21b	60.7d	7.7c	407.95f	13.60d
200kgNPK/ha mulch	74.0a	7.5a	409.58a	13.65a	69.7b	8.8b	714.56c	23.82b
300kgNPK/ha	65.0e	7.1a	295.93d	9.86c	66.0c	7.2c	494.42d	16.48c
300kgNPK/ha mulch	70.0b	7.6a	375.14b	12.50a	71.0a	9.2a	811.16b	27.04a
400kgNPK/ha	67.7b	6.2b	127.22f	4.24d	70.0a	7.1c	442.19e	14.74cd
400kgNPK/ha mulch	68.0b	6.9b	261.30e	8.71c	66.7c	9.6a	866.11a	28.87a

4 MAP = Four months after planting.

Figures followed by the same letters in the same column are not significantly different at 5% (D M R T).

tropical roots/tubers (yam, cassava, sweet potato) cocoyam has even higher potential for food security than the grains such as rice, maize and sorghum (De Vries *et al*; 1976).

Cocoyam cultivation in Nigeria is concentrated in the Southwestern and Southeastern parts of the country due to favourable ecological conditions in these areas. Cultivation is mainly in the hands of resource-poor farmers who intercrop it with other food crops such as yams, cassava, maize, plantain and vegetable (Devos and Wilson, 1978). The high cost of the preferred tubers like yam and the increased awareness of the industrial and export potential of cassava which is widely consumed in Nigeria in various food forms is fast converting cassava to a cash crop. This has given way to high patronage of the relatively obscure crops like cocoyam. Nigeria's current level of production of cocoyam estimated at 11.0 million tones annually is grossly inadequate to satisfy the increasing demand for the crop as alternative food crop. The situation is further worsened especially as cassava which is widely consumed in various food forms in the country is fast becoming an industrial and export crop for foreign exchange earning (Ikwelle *et al*; 2003).

Chemical fertilizers have been used to increase crop yields substantially (Obiefuna, 1987; Spencer, 1988; Swennen, 1990) but continuous sole use of inorganic fertilizers results in soil fertility degradation (Braid and Wilson, 1980; Swennen, 1990; Rhodes, 1993). Emphasis in soil fertility management for sustainable productivity has now shifted from sole inorganic fertilization to integrated nutrient management involving utilization of available organic and inorganic sources of nutrients in a judicious and efficient way. Judicious combination of organic resources with inorganic fertilizers can ensure immediate nutrient release for present crop as well as the long-term build up of soil nutrients (Franzuebbers *et al*; 1998).

In the traditional cultivation of cocoyam and other crops such as plantain/banana regular cultivation practices include mulching and manuring (Udealor *et al*; 1987). Fresh leaves, dry grass, crop refuse, dead leaves, palm fronds, compost manures made up of household sweepings, animals refuse and decayed leaves, are often used to serve both as mulch material and source of organic matter (Udealor *et al*; 1987; Swennen, 1990; Salau *et al*; 1992). The quantity of these materials available to individual farmers is limited especially crop refuse that have competitive uses as livestock feeds. These materials are less persistent and may not be effective as mulch material for a crop like cocoyam which has a long growing season (Ikwelle *et al*; 2003). The need to evaluate the suitability of sawdust which is highly persistent due to its slow rate of decomposition (Obiefuna, 1986) as a mulch material for cocoyam was the basis for this trial.

Table 2. Yield (Corms + cormels) of cocoyam (*Xanthosoma sagittifolium* (L) as influenced by sawdust mulch (20 t/ha) and N P K fertilizer rates (kg/ha) in 2000/2001 and 2001/2002 cropping seasons (t/ha).

Treatment	Cropping Season		Total productivity (t/ha)
	2000/2001	2001/2002	
Control	3.6g	5.5g	9.1g
Sawdust mulch	5.7f	11.3f	17.0f
200kg NPK/ha	10.2e	11.3f	21.5e
200kgNPK/ha + mulch	13.5d	17.0d	30.5d
300kgNPK/ha	12.8d	15.7e	28.5d
300kgNPK/ha + mulch	16.5c	19.3c	35.8c
400kgNPK/ha	18.9b	21.0b	39.9b
400kgNPK/ha + mulch	22.6a	23.4a	46.0a

Figures followed by the same letters in the same column are not significantly different at 5% (D M R T).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study was conducted at the Teaching and Research Farm of the University of Calabar. The area is characterized by a humid tropical climate with about 9 – 10 months of rainy season and a short dry season. Mean annual rainfall is about 2000 – 3000 mm while the mean relative humidity is about 78% and typical of the rain forest region of southeastern Nigeria (Harold, 1971). This site of the experiment falls within the traditional cocoyam producing area of Cross River State (Unama *et al*; 1985).

The soil type of the site is a low base status sandy loam characterized as an Ultisol (Eshett, 1987). Chemical characteristics of the soil were pH (H₂O) 5.45, organic carbon 1.39%, total N. 0.15%, organic matter content 3.34%, available P. 56.4 mg/kg, E C E C 6.75 cmol/kg, exchangeable Na, K, Ca, Mg were 0.11, 0.14, 3.2 and 0.6 cmol/kg respectively.

The land was cleared manually and the vegetation packed away before ploughing using a spade. Plots measured 10.0m x 3.0m (30m²) and were demarcated by 1.0m wide paths. Clean healthy setts of white upland cocoyam (*Xanthosoma sagittifolium* (L). Each weighing approximately 300g were planted in small heaps about 30cm wide at the base and 20cm deep, spaced 1.0m x 1.0m (10,000plants/ha). Planting of cocoyam was done on 15 June, 2004 and 10 April, 2005 for 2000/2001 and 2001/2002 cropping season respectively. During each planting, 15g of Furadan 10G were applied in the planting hole to control the cocoyam root knot nematodes and termites that may attack the sprouting setts.

Treatments studied were control, sawdust mulch at 20t/ha, and N P K 20:10:10 fertilizer rates at 200, 300 and 400 kg/ha each applied sole and in combination with 20 t/ha sawdust mulch (S D M). Each treatment was replicated three times in randomized complete block (R C B) design.

Sawdust mulch was applied immediately after planting cocoyam in such a way that the entire plot was completely and permanently covered with 3±0.5cm thick sawdust layer until cocoyam was harvested when all the leaves withered in January.

The land was ploughed again during the second year (2001/2002) planting to incorporate the partially decomposed sawdust in order to increase the organic matter content of the soil. Fresh sawdust was reapplied just like in the first year.

Each fertilizer rate was divided into two equal portions and the first portion applied broadcast on the entire plot at one month after planting to enhance vegetative growth. The second portion was applied at three months of growth which coincides with the period of enlargement of new corms and cormels.

Plots were maintained weed free throughout the duration of the experiment by hand hoeing and hand pulling during which soil was added to the base of cocoyam plants to promote corm/cormel development and to cover exposed corms/cormels as they are superficially oriented.

Data on vegetative growth collected at four months after planting and corm yield were statistically analyzed using analysis of variance (A N O V A) technique. Significant means were separated using Duncan Multiple Range Test (D M R T) at $p = 0.05$.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The vegetative parameters of cocoyam measured were significantly ($p = 0.05$) influenced by sawdust mulch and fertilizer rates in both 2000/2001 and 2001/2002 cropping seasons (Table 1). Cocoyam plants in mulched plots fertilized at 100 kg/ha were significantly ($p = 0.05$) taller bearing more leaves per plant with higher leaf area and LAI than cocoyam in other plots. Taller cocoyam with more leaves were observed in mulched plots fertilized at 200 kg/ha while the highest LA and LAI were obtained in mulched plots fertilized at 300 kg/ha of fertilizer in 2001/2002 cropping season (Table 1).

Cocoyam plants in control plots were least in all the growth indices measured while application of sawdust mulch even without fertilizer compared well with plants fertilized at 100 kg/ha. Cocoyams fertilized above 100 kg/ha with or without sawdust mulch were superior to those that received only sawdust mulch in all vegetative indices measured.

Cocoyams that were jointly mulched and fertilized were superior as they grew more luxuriantly than plants in other treatments. Among the combined mulch and fertilized treatments the fertilizer rates at 200 kg/ha promoted the best cocoyam vegetative growth. Higher rates inhibited plant height, leaf formation and expansion, and leaf area index. The favourable growth exhibited by fertilized mulched cocoyams at the lowest fertilizer rate (200 kg/ha) in the first season crop (2001/2002) probably was because the soil fertility was still adequate and low levels of applied were adequate for optimum growth of cocoyam. However, as cultivation extended to the second year cropping (2001/2002 cropping season), high levels of applied nutrients were needed for optimum cocoyam growth due to nutrient uptake by the previous crop. This could explain the best growth performance of the crop in plots fertilized with the highest fertilizer rate (300 kg/ha). This observation is consistent with Udoh *et al*, (2005) who recommended 200 – 300 kg/ha of N P K fertilizer for optimum performance of cocoyam.

Cocoyam corm yield varied among the various treatments and between the two cropping seasons. Yields were highest in mulched plots fertilized at 400 kg/ha and lowest in control plots in both 2000/2001 and 2001/2002 cropping seasons (Table 2). Sawdust mulch applied sole raised cocoyam yield by 2.1 t/ha (37%) and 5.8 t/ha (51%) above the control in 2000/2001 and 2001/2002 respectively, but higher yields were obtained by combining sawdust mulch with fertilizer at all rates than the corresponding fertilizer rate applied sole. Combining sawdust mulch with fertilizer at 200, 300 and 400 kg/ha in 2000/2001, cocoyam yields were higher than in the control by 9.9 t/ha (73%), 12.9 t/ha (79%) and 19.0 t/ha (84%) respectively. A similar yield scenario was obtained in 2001/2002 when the yield increases over the control in the corresponding fertilizer rates were 17.5 t/ha (68%), 13.8 t/ha (72%), and 17.9 t/ha (76%).

Optimum cocoyam yield obtained by jointly applying sawdust mulch with 400 kg/ha of fertilizer probably indicates adequacy of this level of fertilization which agrees with the recommendation of Udoh *et al*; (2005) that for optimum yield cocoyam should be fertilized with 200 – 300 kg/ha of N P K fertilizer. This experiment has shown that combined application of sawdust mulch and N P K fertilizer enhanced cocoyam productivity indicating the benefit of integrated nutrient management in cocoyam production. In addition to enhanced fertilizer use efficiency (Swennen, 1990; Gichuru *et al*; 2003), sawdust mulch obviously created favourable micro environmental conditions (Swennen, 1990) which promoted the growth and corm development. Low yields obtained in 2000/2001 cropping season could have been due to delayed or late planting in June, 2001 as well as the attack by the cocoyam yield decline disease known as the cocoyam root rot blight complex (C R R B C) observed in some plots. Higher yields recorded in 2001/2002 could be attributed to early planting in April which afforded the crop a long growing period for optimum dry matter accumulation. A possible increase in soil

fertility arising from incorporation of partially decomposed sawdust mulch into the soil during ploughing for the second cropping in 2001/2002 could also contribute or account for the high yield of the second crop.

Corm yields however, remained stable in the second cropping season (2001/2002) in plots that were jointly mulched and fertilized. Stable crop yields due to application of organic mulches has also been documented by Kang and Duguma (1985)¹; Obiefuna (1986) Mulongoy and Akobundu (1992); Salau *et al*; (1992).

CONCLUSION

Joint application of sawdust mulch and N P K fertilizer promoted cocoyam growth and yield. Corm yields increased with increasing rates of fertilizer and optimum yield was obtained at the fertilizer rate of 400 kg/ha combined with sawdust mulch. Cocoyam farmers should adopt this practice as a strategy to boost the productivity of the crop which has high nutritional value and potential and is fast emerging as a food security staple in Nigeria.

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